

Challenges and recommendations for longitudinal tensile testing of unidirectional composites based on a round-robin programme

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The challenges of tensile testing composites

Stress concentrations

Failure near the grips/tabs

Difficult to detect failure location

6 specimen designs and 7 labs

Minor differences in modulus between labs

Minor differences in strength and failure strain

Some differences in measured strength

Continuous tabs: mainly due to inaccuracy in stress back-calculation

Thick butterfly: premature splitting + size effect (3-5.5%)

Very consistent failure strain values

Diamond disk or water jet cutting?

Don't apply too much gripping force

Enough to avoid slippage, but no more!

Detecting the failure location

Observing postmortem = impossible

Two solutions:

Continuous tabs

High-speed imaging at 10 Mfps

Reference

+0.1 ms

+0.2 ms

+0.3 ms

+0.4 ms

+0.5 ms

Recommendations

Lab-to-lab variations larger than design-to-design variations

→ Reliably measurements possible, if:

Very well aligned fibres, plies, and cutting

High-quality edge

Non-standardised designs: high failure strain and strength

Standardised designs: almost as good

Sandwich coupons: great for failure strain

Thick butterfly specimens underperformed, but different purpose

Recommendations

Determine failure location: 1000 fps camera or faster

Non-contact strain measurements methods preferred

Discard specimens with significant load drops (>3% of tensile strength)

Desired outcome:
Minor modifications to test standards

Final notes

All data available: <https://zenodo.org/records/12771361>

A request from all benchmark exercises and round-robins:

Appreciate us

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